

e

Project Proposition

Collaboration in
Innovative Technologies
2022 (CIT 2022)

e

General

Please refer to the Call for Proposals “Call for Collaboration in Innovative Technologies (CIT 2022)” for the Terms and Conditions of this granting scheme. The call text is available at <http://www.esciencecenter.nl/calls-for-proposals>.

Proposals must be submitted using the ISAAC submission system: www.isaac.nwo.nl (see below for details).

The proposition should be written in English. The layout of the proposition should facilitate easy reading. Use the Verdana font at font size 8.5 (or similar).

REGISTRATION FORM (BASIC DATA)

1. Details of the applicant

1a. Lead Applicant (LA). The Lead Applicant (LA) is the contact person for all correspondence.

Name, first name, title(s)	
Position	
Employment (fixed term/temporary)	
Institute	
Department	
Section	
Address	
Postcode	
City	
Telephone	
E-mail	

2a. Title of the project proposition and acronym

A short and specific title for the proposed research. The title entered here must be the same as the title submitted to the ISAAC submission system. Please also use a project acronym as part of the title.

2b. Keywords

(max. 6 keywords)

2c. Technology area

Indicate the technology area of the proposed work. Please use exactly one of the tick boxes to select one of the below technology areas. Submitted proposals compete within the selected technology area only.

- Digital Twins: Virtual Representations of the Real World
- SciML: Combining Machine Learning with Scientific Domain Knowledge

2d. Link with eScience Center expertise

Indicate the area(s) of expertise the proposed work is expected to require. In case your research does not exactly match one of the options, but you are of the opinion that your project idea still fits well within the aims and scope of the call, please direct your questions to open-calls@esciencecenter.nl.

- Software quality: developing workflow technologies, improving software practices, advancing software sustainability
- AI: machine learning, image processing
- Analytics: big data analytics, text analysis, visualization
- Data processing: databases, real-time data analysis, interoperability and linked data
- Computing: exploitation of hardware accelerators, high performance computing, cloud computing, combining simulations

PROJECT PROPOSITION

3. Description of the project proposition (max. 600 words)

The description should be text only (i.e. without figures). For sections 3a and 3b combined no more than 600 words may be used, excluding literature references and key publications. References are allowed in this section, but the description should be self-contained. The project proposition should cover:

3a. Outline the envisaged applied technologies. (max. 400 words)

- Describe the technological innovations that can potentially be transformed into an applied technology;
- Describe the applied technology;
- Make clear why eScience Center expertise is required to achieve the project's aims.

3b. What is the expected impact? (max. 200 words)

- Describe the impact the applied technology is expected to have across the disciplines. Include three examples of impact.

3c. Two key publications in the field covered by the project proposition.

- Please list 2 key publications by the LA, relevant to the proposal, and not older than 7 years.

ADMINISTRATIVE DETAILS

ATTACHED DOCUMENTS

This project proposition needs the following documents:

- A Letter of Commitment signed by the authorized signatory of the institution at which the Lead Applicant is employed, detailing the Lead Applicant's investment in the project (minimally 0.3 FTE per year). Use the template available on the eScience Center website (<http://www.esciencecenter.nl/calls-for-proposals>).

PROPOSAL SUBMISSION

The proposition should be submitted as a PDF file via the electronic application system ISAAC **before Thursday 12 May 2022, 14:00 CET**. More information on the use of ISAAC is available at www.nwo.nl. The proposal must be submitted from the ISAAC account of the Lead Applicant.

For technical questions about the use of ISAAC, please contact the ISAAC helpdesk. Applicants are requested to read the ISAAC manual before consulting the helpdesk. The ISAAC helpdesk is available from Monday to Friday from 10:00 to 17:00 hours on +31 (0)20 346 7179. You can also send your questions by email to isaac.helpdesk@nwo.nl. You will receive a reply within two working days.

MORE INFORMATION

For more information, please check www.esciencecenter.nl or contact:

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